

Karan Kumar Prasad

(B.E. in Mechanical Engineering)

SLIET, Longowal, Sangrur

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Objective

Eager to learn and expand my skills through your organization to succeed in an environment of growth and excellence and earn a job which provides me satisfaction and self-development and helps me to achieve organizational goals.

Educational Qualification

- Completed Bachelor of Engineering, with Mechanical Engineering as core subject from Sant Longowal Institute of Engineering and Technology, Longowal(SLIET)Punjab with 7.0 SGPA (2018-2021).
- Completed ICD(Integrated Certificate Diploma) Mechanical Engineering as core subject, from Sant Longowal Institute of Engineering and Technology, Longowal Punjab with 6.27 SGPA (2015-2018).
- Completed Secondary (Matriculation), from Raj High School, Dumraon (BIHAR) affiliated to BSEB with 70% in 2015.

Work Profile Details:

- ❖ Timely completion of work assigned by seniors & team mates.
- ❖ Operation & maintenance of HVAC & Water system equipment.
- ❖ Operating BMS for maintaining required environment conditions in plant area.
- ❖ Qualification & Requalification of HVAC systems(URS,DQ,IQ,OQ and PQ).
- ❖ Performing documentation and compliance to HVAC Clean Room validation like Air flow, Air Velocity, Filter Integrity and NVPC.
- ❖ Planning for execution of water systems related activities like PM, MGF Backwash, ACF Backwash, Softener Regeneration, Dosing NaOCL, SMBS, NaOH, Cleaning of RO Membrane, Chemical Sanitization, Hot Water Sanitization, Storage Tank

Cleaning, Vent Filter Integrity Test, Cartridge Filter Replacement.

- ❖ Maintain daily log book in Water System.
- ❖ Periodic Monitoring of HVAC systems.
- ❖ Exposure for installation and qualification documents preparations for HVAC equipment like AHU, Dehumidifier, Humidifier, Dust Extraction System and VAC etc.
- ❖ Operation and Preventive Maintenance execution of AHU, Dehumidifier, Humidifier, DEX, and VAC etc.
- ❖ Coordinate with the user department for equipment maintenance and filter cleaning of AHU.
- ❖ Coordinate with vendors for HVAC Periodic Monitoring and all test execution as per ISO-14644.
- ❖ HEPA Filter replacement activity & performing applicable tests during filter replacement.
- ❖ Audit preparation and compliance according to standard guidelines.
- ❖ Issuance of spares from engineering store as per requirement during Preventive, Predictive or Breakdown maintenance.
- ❖ Have experience in Compressed Air Testing.

Professional Experience (Total- 3 year 4 months)

- Worked as an Apprentice (Engineering Department) in “Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd, Location-Baddi(HP)” in “HVAC section” from 02-Nov-2021 to 15-July-2022
- Worked as Junior Engineer under utility O&M department in Baxter India Pvt Ltd, Location - Ahmedabad, Gujarat from 22-July-2022 to 19-Feb-2024
- Currently working as Executive (Engineering Department) in “Torrent Pharmaceuticals Ltd, Location-Baddi(HP)” in “HVAC section”

Personal Details

- Date of Birth : 19 JUNE 2000
- Languages known : Hindi ,English
- Father’s Name : Satyendra Kumar Prasad
- Mother’s Name : Renu Devi
- Nationality : Indian
- Hobbies and Interests : Traveling,Foodie,Web Surfing

